

LINCOLN UNIVERSITY COLLEGE

An Investigation of the Effects of Reward and Punishment in Promoting Classroom Discipline among Pre-Primary and Primary Teachers at Indian Schools in Muscat, Oman

Proposal Report

By

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ABSTRACT

Establishing discipline in modern classrooms is a challenge for most educators. This study was designed to examine the impact of reward and punishment on the behaviour of children in selected Indian primary and preschool schools in Oman. This study was motivated to find out if teachers were supportive of the use of reward and punishment in these school systems. The investigation is therefore guided by the following: Does reward and punishment have any effect on the education system in primary schools. If reward and punishment were the discipline tools to be followed, the questionnaire would have been implemented. The results have been analysed, the latter emerging as search results. Reward and punishment play an important role in the teaching and learning process and should be implemented in schools. Teachers advocate the use of reward and punishment in the school system. Reward and punishment are descriptive weapons and they play an important role in school management, academic achievement and student behaviour issues.

CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

Teachers face many challenges in the classroom during teaching learning process and one of the main challenges is management of the Class. Behaviour management is an important aspect of the classroom management. All teachers are bound to encounter some kind misconduct or disciplinary problems. Misbehaviour is an activity which affects overall class room environment (Ding, Li, & Kulm, 2008). Misbehaviours among school students in classrooms are a factor leading adversely to teaching learning climate (John, 2013). The adverse effects can be categorized from the most damaging to the least detrimental. Misbehaviours in the classroom destroy the class atmosphere and the teaching process which hinder both students and teachers from achieving their goals and contribute to time management problems. In class misbehaviours endanger teachers and students alike (Özben, 2010). One of the means through which a teacher can maintain class discipline is through reward and punishment. The method that can be used by teachers to motivate students is by giving rewards and punishments.

Kompri (2016: 289) Reward means a reward, prize, award, or reward. Reward as an educational tool is given when a child does something good, or has achieved a target. In the concept of education, reward is a tool to increase the motivation of students. This method can associate someone's actions and behaviour with feelings of happiness, pleasure, and will usually make them do a good deed repeatedly. Appreciation is an element of discipline that is very important in the development of self and behaviour of children. A person will continue to strive to improve and maintain discipline if the implementation of the discipline results in achievement and productivity which then gets an award.

Kompri (2016: 291) punishment is defined as punishment or sanctions. Punishment is usually carried out when certain targets are not achieved, or there is a child's behaviour that is not in accordance with the norms believed by the school. If the reward is a form of reinforcement positive ones; then punishment is a form of negative reinforcement, but if it is given correctly and wisely it can be a motivational tool for students to live a disciplined life. Therefore, this research presents an opportunity to explore how teachers approach student behaviour in context of their daily teaching and how they conceptualise and understand their practice.

A. *Background of the Study*

Early Childhood Education and Primary Education lay the foundation for students' formal education by introducing new concepts that develop in the various subjects they will learn throughout their careers in school. Rewards and Punishments in these schools are used on daily basis to encourage discipline. In some cases, students should be rewarded for good deeds and in other cases they should be punished for bad actions.

➤ *Discipline*

Current practices in classroom management do not seem to be eliminating the classroom discipline problems. Freiberg and Lamb (2009) stated that the issue of school discipline is one of the top three educational concerns. Educators and researchers have agreed that the teacher has the primary responsibility for classroom management, and have found that, in most situations, the teacher defines the rules and consequences for misbehaviour (Freiberg & Lamb, 2009). Additionally, researchers supported the principle that communication between teachers and students regarding a discipline problem is beneficial to the learning environment (Freiberg & Lamb, 2009). Nevertheless, some students will create disruptions depending on the environment they inhabit (Bru, 2009). A few studies have depicted how, with the use of effective classroom management, a teacher can change the classroom environment from one of problems and inadequate learning to a positive learning environment (Beaty-O'Farrell, Green, & Hanna, 2010; Flutter, 2006). However, researchers have not fully identified the classroom management practices that are most effective in reducing classroom disruptions and promoting an environment that will enable learning. A notable classroom management practice was Caring Behaviour Management (CBM), which uses six integral components to create a positive learning environment (Paciotti, 2010). Other practices included the PRAISE note system to promote appropriate behaviours in school and the 12 practical strategies to diffuse classroom disruptions (Shukla-Mehta & Albin, 2003; Wheatley et al., 2009).

Students that are disciplined often arrive at school on time, follow all rules, and conduct themselves in accordance with accepted standards. A set of behaviours and a procedure that demonstrate the importance of order and compliance combine to generate discipline. It is expected to create a comfortable and peaceful learning environment in the classroom (Rachman & Agustian, 2016). The results of Sutrisno's research (2019) confirm that students' undisciplined behaviour is shown by their daily behaviour at school, such as truancy, arriving late, neglecting assignments, incomplete lesson notes, not in full uniform, lazy to follow lessons, indifferent to class time, smoking, being rude, influencing friends to violate discipline, hanging out at the cafe near the school, and acting hyperactive in class. These students know that if they are not disciplined there will be sanctions, but they are still undisciplined because they cannot control themselves. Still in the same study, there are also research subjects who are quiet and always polite to teachers, but in reality, they often violate discipline at school. Rewards and the method of punishment used by educators to stimulate children's discipline to be more enthusiastic in learning and develop good habits of character, as well as prevent possible character misalignment performed by a child.

➤ *Rewards and Punishments*

Hanna (2015) noted that Classroom discipline is more than the following. It is more than the power the teacher exercises over his students, mere maintenance of law and order in the classroom or the right method of dealing with offenders in schools, punishment and occasional praises and rewards, mere stillness and quietness in the classroom, discipline according to scholars, it is the application of all those influence which secure or at least try to secure proper conduct in schools. Mansfield (2017) shows students' perception of reward and punishment has been found to impact on their recognition and sense of belonging in the school, which in turn have implications student academic performance and social behaviour. The results of Surbakti's research (2019) state that reward is one way or educational tool to educate students to feel happy because their actions and work are rewarded. In more detail, there are several rewards such as praise, awards, and material prizes. According to Emily (2012), punishment is the authoritative imposition of something negative or unpleasant on a person or animal in response to behaviour deemed wrong by an individual or group. Hermanto (2020) stated that there is a significant influence between the provision of punishment on student learning discipline. In Misriyah's research (2015), the reward has implications for increasing motivation to take action according to character education values.

The balance in implementing reward and punishment is very important to keep the response going as expected by the teacher focused on giving punishment for every mistake without seeing the kindness done by the child will cause the child to become rebellious person and easily lie, this is in line with what Imam Al-Ghazali said, one of the leading Islamic philosophers (Fuji Rahmadi, 2016).

Rewards and the method of punishment used by educators to stimulate children's discipline to be more enthusiastic in learning and develop good habits of character, as well as prevent possible character misalignment performed by a child.

B. Problem Statement

Discipline is most important in one's life and development. As intended by nature, children they constantly make mistakes and it is not uncommon to find kids in primary and pre-primary level exhibiting deviant behaviour which is punishable. Pre-primary and primary school teachers have role in ensuring that cases of indiscipline encountered are handled appropriately using a variety of disciplinary approaches.

"Teachers' understanding of the reward and punishment method has not yet developed, due to lack of insight into the reward and punishment method itself, plus many teachers still prioritize giving punishment for mistakes made by students compared to rewarding the efforts made by students".

In the pre and primary Indian schools of Oman in Muscat region, the instances of indiscipline are not rare. How teachers in this area solve these problems using rewards and punishments is the main driving force for this study. This study therefore seeks to test the effectiveness of using rewards and punishments in motivating good discipline in pre and primary school students

C. Aims and Objectives

➤ *General Objective*

The purpose of this study is to investigate the effectiveness of use of rewards and punishment in promoting classroom discipline in pre and primary Indian schools in Muscat, Oman

➤ *Specific Objectives*

• *This study is Guided by the following Specific Objectives:*

- ✓ Investigate the influence of rewards on classroom discipline among pre and primary school children.
- ✓ Investigate the influence of punishment on classroom discipline among pre and primary school children.
- ✓ To find out the most appropriate method, reward or punishment followed by the teachers to achieve, student discipline.

D. Research Questions

• *This Research Paper has the following Research Questions;*

- ✓ What is the impact of reward on promoting classroom discipline?
- ✓ What is the impact of punishment on promoting classroom discipline?
- ✓ What is the best strategy used by the teachers to maintain discipline in the classroom?

E. Hypothesis

- H1-Rewards is positively influence the promotion of classroom discipline in pre-primary and primary Indian schools in Muscat
- H2-Punishment is negatively influence the in promoting classroom discipline in pre-primary and primary Indian schools in Muscat

F. Variables

In this Research there are two Independent Variables. They are:

- Reward
- Punishment

This research is intended to investigate the effectiveness of rewards and punishments in maintaining classroom discipline in Indian schools of Muscat region in Oman.

G. Significance of the Study

➤ *The Significance of this Research is as follows;*

Early childhood education can be described as the most important point to ensure success in education in an individual's academic life. By focusing on aspects of the discipline, this study hopes to find various expressions of discipline and to highlight how rewards and punishments used by teachers to deal with these situations as they arise.

This study provides an expanded knowledge to teachers, parents, educational planners, and instructors about the use of more effective rewards and punishments to reinforce respect for human rights and property of pre and primary school children. It is also helpful to enlighten education stakeholders on how to apply effectively rewards and punishments to improve class room discipline in students. In addition, the study wishes to help and highlight some of the challenges that a pre and primary school teachers face when teaching so that these problems can be treated more meaningfully than they do now.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

Many researches and studies associated with the importance, effects and policy on discipline were made in order to perceive the importance of discipline in schools. Discipline plays a significant role in achieving organizational standards. Discipline helps to control negative behaviour and promotes positive behaviour such as obedience. School discipline is a form of discipline implemented at school to regulate students and maintain order.

Positive discipline is Holistic, it applies not only to students' behaviour, but to all aspects of their learning and social interactions. It is strength-based, as it identifies and builds on the students' strengths. It is Constructive, aimed at strengthening students' self-esteem and confidence. It is Inclusive, for it recognizes and respects the diversity of all students.

Next, it is Pro-active as it identifies the roots of behavioural and learning difficulties and implement strategies promoting success, avoid conflict, and finally, it is participatory in the learning process and school community (Durrant, 2013; Ingersoll, 2001; Kohn, 2006).

But by implementing the positive discipline model, you can use conflict as an indicator to promote proper management emotions and resolve conflict without hurting others physically or emotionally. Before any action taken, one must look into the variety of reasons that lead to a child's misbehaviour. Children have different stages of development too. Make a list of the possible reasons and assess the child's behaviour, remember your long-term goals and think the characteristics that you hope your students will develop. Once you have thought through the problem, use positive discipline then involve the student in thinking in finding solutions to challenges and difficulties (Finn, Fish, & Scott 2008; Durrant, 2013; Jackson, 1993; Anbar & Eker, 2007). Furthermore, the process of discipline includes the protection, prevention, guidance and correction of abnormal behaviour.

The application of Rewards and Punishment will be very helpful in disciplining students. Imron states that this happens because when a child performs instructions well, he will get an award for his efforts to be good, and something fun will always be a stimulus for repeated good responses. Meanwhile, the reward (appreciation) is balanced with the provision of punishment so that children do not occasionally try to violate as well as provide a deterrent effect for children who commit violations not to repeat themselves, Purwanto (2016: 186).

The balance in implementing reward and punishment is very important to keep the response going as expected by the teacher. focused on giving punishment for every mistake without seeing the kindness done by the child will cause the child to become a rebellious person and easily lie, this is in line with what Imam Al-Ghazali said, one of the leading Islamic philosophers (Fuji Rahmadi, 2016). Focused on giving rewards for every good without acting on every mistake made by the child will make the child become selfish and also spoiled too (Anna Novita, 2015).

Rina (2017) conducted a research which results showed that, (1) Reward gives effect to emotional intelligence through student's ability to recognize and manage their own emotions, empathy and cooperation, (2) Punishment gives effect to emotional intelligence according to Daniel Goleman, with emotional intelligence, emotions will be controlled, so arises a sense of calm and peace, (3) Goleman's concept of emotional intelligence through the giving of reward and punishment has a positive impact that both aims to shape a good human person.

According to Sabartiningsih (2018), reward is a way for someone to give an award to someone for doing the right thing, so that someone can be enthusiastic about doing certain tasks and be more motivated to do something else and the process is better. so that a person is able to achieve success from something he does. Punishment is an action given by educators to students who have made mistakes, with the aim that students will not repeat it again and will correct the mistakes that have been made. A punishment is appropriate to be given to students if the misery caused has positive and pedagogical values.

➤ *Reward:*

The term reward is broadly defined as a tool that teachers use to try and reinforce a desired behaviour (Witzel & Mercer, 2003). The elements that determine the effectiveness of a reward are how it is delivered by the teacher and how it is perceived by the student (Witzel & Mercer). Rewards are of different types such as Praises, Stickers, Stars, Candy, Gifts, A note of praise, new pencil, Extra recess etc offered by the teachers to encourage good discipline in students.

➤ *Punishment:*

Classroom punishment is a way to help control the environment so that the students who want to succeed in school have the opportunity to do so in an effective classroom for learning. Punishment techniques help maintain a discipline and professional environment to improve learning. Types of punishments used in the classroom by teachers are suspension, extra homework, scolding, pinching, isolation, hitting with hands or stick, pulling ears, being sent to the principal etc. this will help to discourage the bad discipline in students. This research has one dependent variable that is discipline.

➤ *Discipline:*

Discipline is defined as teaching others to follow rules or standards by using punishment to correct undesirable behaviour and by rewards to generate or retain desirable behaviour. In a classroom, a teacher uses discipline to ensure that order is maintained, school rules are enforced, and students are in a safe learning environment.

A. *Theoretical Framework*

The aim of this study is to examine the effect of reward and punishment on the disciplinary issues of elementary school students in Muscat within the theoretical framework of B.F.Skinner's theory of operant conditioning.

Skinner's famous experiment with rats in a Skinner box showed that rats can learn to respond to stimuli in certain ways to win food as a reward and avoid being electrocuted as punishment for a bad choice plan. operant conditioning is a type of learning that occurs when certain behaviours are rewarded or punished.

Using operant conditioning in the classroom can be beneficial in many ways. But the most important effect, is the implementation of classroom techniques. Using positive conditioning can give students immediate feedback on their classroom discipline. When teachers reward positive discipline, other students are more likely to copy that discipline in order to receive a reward. Rewarded students were also more likely to repeat the same course due to positive feedback.

Immediate feedback is also helpful in reducing negative disciplinary issues in the classroom. Mild punishment or refusal to praise can be an easy condition in education. When a teacher punishes a disobedient student, other students will want to avoid that punishment and thus will be less likely to rebel. Students who are punished are also less likely to repeat the same thing again.

Most of the research on problem behaviour is based on the behaviour management theory presented by Frederic Skinner. (Winokur S.) He introduced the concept of operant conditioning to change disruptive or encourage desirable behaviour in an individual. Skinner believed that a desirable learning outcome is possible if we can change the learner's behaviour. (Omomia OA 2014) The prevention of problem behaviour in an academic institution now has become an educational policy. Skinner's operant conditioning theory can guide the teaching practices that ultimately result in the development of a desired behaviour and improvement in learning.

Fig 1 Theoretical Framework of Operant Conditioning

CHAPTER THREE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

In this research a quantitative research approach has been used to analyse the Effectiveness of rewards and punishments in maintaining the classroom discipline by the teachers. An exploration of participant's views on managing learners' discipline will be substantially made. A convenience non-probability sampling using snow ball sampling has been used . The participants had been selected from a population based on Non-random pattern. It focused on the analysis of concrete data and figures. This research is going to be a survey to investigate and understand the right method to inculcate classroom discipline in students. The survey approach will be the most suitable strategy for this research.

B. The Setting of the Study

This research was conducted taking teachers as participants who are working in the 5 Indian schools in Oman. Number of Students in each class is 45.

➤ *The Names of the Schools are as follows:*

- ✓ Indian school Muscat.
- ✓ Indian school Darsait.
- ✓ Indian school Wadi-Kabir.
- ✓ Indian school Bousher.
- ✓ Middle east nursery.

C. Population of the Study

The targeted population for the current research is the primary and pre-primary school teachers working in Indian schools in Muscat region. The researcher will be using snowball sample collection technique of the type Exponential non- discriminative and will collect data from 45 participants. The participants will be selected from a population based on Non-random pattern. Only teachers were included in this survey, people from non-teaching background were excluded.

D. Sampling size and Method

- The size of the sample will be 30.
- A convenience non-probability sampling using snow ball technique will be used.
- Exponential non- discriminative snowball method will be used.
- The participants will be selected from a population based on Non-random pattern.

E. Conceptual Framework

Conceptual framework is a written or visual representation of the expected relationships between variables. Variables are simply characteristics or attributes that the researcher wants to study. Conceptual frameworks are often developed on the basis of a literature review of existing research and theories on the topic.

Fig 2 Conceptual Framework

This study will examine the influence of reward and punishment as well as instructor's strategy for reward and punishment applied in the classroom. Here the above figure shows that reward, punishment are the two independent variables or the external stimulus which will help to reach the outcome that is discipline which is a dependent variable. To reach this outcome different types of punishments and rewards will be used by the teachers in the class room.

F. Instruments

- The instrument that will be used in this research to collect data is a questionnaire.
- The questionnaire will be divided into 4 sections:
- 1st section- It will include the demographic data of the participant.
- 2nd section- Contains the practices that teachers employ to discipline the students.
- 3rd section- effectiveness of rewards on the management of student’s discipline problems.
- 4th section – Effectiveness of punishments on the management of student’s discipline problems.
- In this research, the questionnaire will be presented in 5 sections, using a 5-point Likert scale questions based on the number of research variables. (Where 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree and 5 = strongly agree).

G. Procedures

➤ *Data Collection Procedures*

The current study has used data that was collected from surveys. The questionnaire was closed ended in essence to make the data collection process more efficient. A survey questionnaire was done using google forms and questions based on research questions.

➤ *Data Analysis Demographic Data:*

The age distribution indicates that individuals aged 31-40 are most interested in investigating the effects of reward and punishment on classroom discipline, with 60% of respondents in this age group. Respondents aged 41-50 are less interested, with those below 20 and over 50 less likely to be interested. Females are more likely to be interested in investigating reward and punishment’s effects on classroom discipline, with 82.20% of respondents female, while 17.80% are male. However, gender doesn’t determine interest or expertise, and individuals of any gender can offer valuable perspectives. The study focuses on the effects of reward and punishment on classroom discipline, with 71.1% of respondents holding a Master's degree. 15.6% hold a Bachelor's degree, and 11.1% hold a Doctorate or another degree. Individuals with 11-20 years of experience are most interested in investigating reward and punishment's effects on classroom discipline, with 42.2% of respondents. Less experienced (42.2%), 21-30 years (11.2%), and only 4.4% have 30 years or more experience. Teaching hours distribution shows that those with 4-6 hours or more are most interested in investigating the effects of reward and punishment on classroom discipline. 31.1% of respondents teach 4 hours or more, while 26.7% teach 5 hours or more.

Table 1 Types of Rewards and Punishments used by the Teachers

TYPES OF REWARDS AND PUNISHMENTS USED BY THE TEACHERS	STRONGLY AGREED	AGREED	NEUTRAL	DISAGREED	STRONGLY DISAGREED
Talked it over with the child	24.40%	60.00%	11.10%	4.40%	0.00%
Ignored the bad behaviour	4.40%	15.50%	22.20%	31.10%	24.40%
Verbally reprimanded the child	8.90%	28.90%	42.20%	11.10%	6.10%
Tried to teach better behaviour	51.10%	40%	6.70%	0.00%	0.00%
Used praise to encourage better behaviour	62.20%	35.60%	2.20%	0.00%	0.00%
sent the child to the corner /back of the room	6.70%	8.90%	17.80%	48.90%	13.30%
sent the child out of class (time out)	4.40%	13.30%	15.60%	37.60%	24.40%
removed privileges (e.g loss of recess)	4.40%	20.00%	20%	35.60%	15.60%
detained the child	2.20%	13.30%	17.60%	42.20%	22.20%
contacted child's parents	28.90%	60.00%	8.90%	0.00%	0.00%
sent the child to the principal /executive	4.40%	40.00%	33.30%	17.80%	0.00%
consulted with school /district social worker	11.10%	44.40%	26.70%	11.10%	2.20%
used seating arrangements	20.00%	66.70%	11.10%	0.00%	0.00%
adapted curriculum to suit the child's needs	28.90%	60.00%	8.90%	0.00%	0.00%
used token economics	6.70%	42.20%	44.40%	4.40%	2.20%
used conflict resolution methods	24.40%	48.90%	13.30%	8.90%	0.00%
called class meetings or discussion	22.20%	62.20%	13.30%	0.00%	0.00%
implemented peer support program	33.30%	48.90%	15.60%	0.00%	0.00%
used behaviour modification	33.30%	55.60%	8.90%	0.00%	0.00%
referred students for or given corporal punishment (spanking)	4.40%	15.60%	22.20%	31.10%	26.70%

➤ *Talked it over with the Child:*

Fig 3 Talked it over with the Child

Based on the given distribution of responses about whether the respondents have talked over issues of classroom discipline with their children, it appears that a majority of respondents (84.4%) have talked about this issue with their children, either strongly agreeing (24.4%) or agreeing (60.0%) with the statement. Only a small percentage of respondents were neutral (11.1%) or disagreed (4.4%) with the statement.

➤ *Ignored the bad Behaviour:*

Fig 4 Ignored the bad Behaviour

Based on the given distribution of responses about whether the respondents ignore bad behaviour in the classroom, it appears that a plurality of respondents (31.1%) disagree with the statement, while 24.4% strongly disagree, and only 20% of respondents agree with the statement, either strongly (4.4%) or simply (15.6%). A larger percentage of respondents were neutral (22.2%) on the issue.

➤ *Verbally Reprimanded the Child:*

Fig 5 Verbally Reprimanded the Child

Based on the given distribution of responses about whether the respondents have verbally reprimanded a child for bad behaviour in the classroom, it appears that a plurality of respondents (42.2%) were neutral on the issue, while 28.9% agreed and 8.9% strongly agreed with the statement. A smaller percentage of respondents disagreed (11.1%) or strongly disagreed (6.7%) with the statement.

➤ *Tried to Teach Better Behaviour:*

Based on the given distribution of responses about whether the respondents have tried to teach better behaviour in the classroom, it appears that a large majority of respondents (91.1%) either strongly agree (51.1%) or agree (40%) with the statement. Only a small percentage of respondents were neutral (6.7%) and none of the respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed with the statement. This suggests that the majority of respondents believe that teaching better behaviour is an important part of promoting classroom discipline.

➤ *Used Praise to Encourage Better Behaviour:*

Based on the given distribution of responses about whether the respondents have used praise to encourage better behaviour in the classroom, it appears that a large majority of respondents (97.8%) either strongly agree (62.2%) or agree (35.6%) with the statement. No respondents were neutral, disagreed or strongly disagreed with the statement. This suggests that using praise to encourage better behaviour is a widely accepted and commonly used approach to promoting classroom discipline.

➤ *Sent the Child to the Corner/Back of the Room:*

Fig 6 Sent the Child to the Corner/ back of the Room.

Based on the given distribution of responses about whether the respondents have sent a child to the corner, back of the room, or other similar disciplinary actions, it appears that a majority of respondents (62.2%) either disagree (48.9%) or strongly disagree (13.3%) with the statement. A smaller percentage of respondents were neutral (17.8%), while only a small minority of respondents agreed (8.9%) or strongly agreed (6.7%) with the statement. This suggests that the use of physical positioning as a disciplinary action is not commonly accepted or used by respondents.

➤ *Sent the Child out of Class (Time out):*

Fig 7 Sent the Child out of Class.

Based on the given distribution of responses about whether the respondents have sent a child out of class as a disciplinary action (time out), it appears that a majority of respondents (62.2%) either disagree (37.8%) or strongly disagree (24.4%) with the statement. A smaller percentage of respondents were neutral (15.6%), while only a small minority of respondents agreed (13.3%) or strongly agreed (4.4%) with the statement. This suggests that sending a child out of class as a disciplinary action is not commonly accepted or used by respondents.

➤ *Removed Privileges (E.g.: Loss of Recess or field trip):*

Based on the distribution of responses about whether the respondents have used the removal of privileges, such as loss of recess or field trips, as a disciplinary action, it appears that a majority of respondents (51.1%) either disagree (35.6%) or strongly disagree (15.6%) with the statement. A smaller percentage of respondents agreed (20%) or strongly agreed (4.4%) with the statement, while an equal percentage were neutral (20%). This suggests that removing privileges as a disciplinary action is not commonly accepted or used by respondents.

➤ *Removed Privileges (E.g.: Loss of Recess or field trip):*

Based on the given distribution of responses about whether the respondents have used the removal of privileges, such as loss of recess or field trips, as a disciplinary action, it appears that a majority of respondents (51.1%) either disagree (35.6%) or strongly disagree (15.6%) with the statement. A smaller percentage of respondents agreed (20%) or strongly agreed (4.4%) with the statement, while an equal percentage were neutral (20%). This suggests that removing privileges as a disciplinary action is not commonly accepted or used by respondents.

➤ *Detained the Child:*

Fig 8 Detained the Child

Based on the distribution of responses about whether the respondents have detained a child as a disciplinary action, it appears that a majority of respondents (64.4%) either disagree (42.2%) or strongly disagree (22.2%) with the statement. A smaller percentage of respondents agreed (13.3%) or strongly agreed (2.2%) with the statement, while an equal percentage were neutral (17.8%). This suggests that detaining a child as a disciplinary action is not commonly accepted or used by respondents

➤ *Contacted Child's Parent:*

Based on the given distribution of responses about whether the respondents have contacted a child's parents as a disciplinary action, it appears that a majority of respondents (88.9%) either strongly agree (28.9%) or agree (60.0%) with the statement. A small percentage of respondents were neutral (8.9%), while none of the respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed with the statement. This suggests that contacting a child's parents as a disciplinary action is commonly accepted and utilized by respondents.

➤ *Sent the Child to the Principal/Executive:*

Based on the distribution of responses about whether the respondents have sent a child to the principal or executive as a disciplinary action, it appears that a significant percentage of respondents (44.4%) either strongly agree (4.4%) or agree (40.0%) with the statement. A sizable percentage of respondents were neutral (33.3%), while a smaller percentage of respondents disagreed (17.8%) with the statement. None of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement. This suggests that sending a child to the principal or executive as a disciplinary action is relatively common, but not universally accepted among respondents.

Consulted with school/district social worker:

Fig 9 Consulted with School/District Social Worker

Based on the given distribution of responses about whether the respondents have consulted with a school/district social worker as a disciplinary action, it appears that a significant percentage of respondents (55.5%) either strongly agree (11.1%) or agree (44.4%) with the statement. A sizable percentage of respondents were neutral (26.7%), while a smaller percentage of respondents disagreed (11.1%) with the statement. Only a very small percentage of respondents (2.2%) strongly disagreed with the statement. This suggests that consulting with a school/district social worker as a disciplinary action is relatively common and accepted among respondents.

➤ *Used Seating Arrangement:*

Fig 10 Used Seating Arrangement.

Based on the survey results, it appears that using seating arrangements is a popular method for promoting classroom discipline, with 20% of respondents strongly agreeing and 66.7% agreeing with its use. Only 11.1% of respondents were neutral about using seating arrangements, and none of the respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed with this method. It can be concluded that using seating arrangements is a widely accepted and effective method for promoting discipline in the classroom.

➤ *Adapted Curriculum to Suit the Child’s Needs:*

Based on the data provided, it seems that the majority of teachers (60%) agree that they have adapted the curriculum to suit the child's needs in promoting classroom discipline. 28.9% of teachers strongly agree with this statement, while only 8.9% are neutral and none disagree or strongly disagree. This suggests that many teachers believe that adapting the curriculum can be an effective strategy for promoting classroom discipline.

➤ *Used Token Economies:*

Token economies are a type of behaviour modification technique that involves rewarding positive behaviour with tokens or points, which can later be exchanged for rewards or privileges. The results of the survey suggest that a significant portion of the respondents (48.9%) either agreed or strongly agreed that they used token economies to encourage better behaviour in the classroom.

➤ *Used Conflict Resolution Methods:*

Fig 11 Used Conflict Resolution Methods.

It seems that the majority of respondents (73.3%) either strongly agree or agree that they used conflict resolution methods when dealing with bad behaviour in the classroom. This suggests that conflict resolution is a common approach among educators to address misbehaviour among students. Only a small percentage of respondents (8.9%) disagreed with this approach.

➤ *Called Class Meeting or Discussion:*

Based on the survey results, it seems that most of the teachers (about 60%) would agree or strongly agree that they contacted the child's parents when dealing with bad behaviour. Additionally, a large percentage of teachers also agreed or strongly agreed that they tried to teach better behaviour (91.1%), used praise to encourage better behaviour (97.8%), and adapted the curriculum to suit the child's needs (88.9%).

However, it also seems that there is a range of approaches used by teachers when dealing with bad behaviour. Some approaches, such as calling a class meeting or discussion (84.4%), using conflict resolution methods (73.3%), and adapting the curriculum to suit the child's needs (88.9%), received relatively high agreement rates. Other approaches, such as detaining the child (15.6%), removing privileges (35.6%), and sending the child out of class (51.1%), received lower agreement rates.

It is worth noting that there were some neutral or disagree responses for some of the items, indicating that not all teachers use the same approach when dealing with bad behaviour. It may be useful to provide professional development opportunities for teachers to learn about and discuss various approaches to managing classroom behaviour.

➤ *Implemented Peer Support Program:*

Fig 12 Implemented Peer Support Program.

The results suggest that the implementation of a peer support program was effective in promoting classroom discipline in pre-primary and primary Indian schools in Muscat. The majority of respondents (82.2%) either strongly agreed or agreed that this program was effective. This indicates that the use of peer support can be a valuable tool in promoting positive behaviour in the classroom.

➤ *Used Behaviour Modification:*

Based on the responses, it appears that behaviour modification is a commonly used approach in promoting classroom discipline. A majority of the respondents either strongly agreed or agreed with using behaviour modification. Only a small percentage of respondents were neutral or disagreed with using this approach. It is worth noting, however, that this survey only represents a sample of individuals and may not be representative of all educators' views on behaviour modification.

➤ *Referred Students for or Given Corporal Punishment (Spanking):*

Fig 13 Referred Students for or given Corporal Punishment

It's important to note that corporal punishment (spanking) is not an appropriate or recommended form of discipline in schools. It can lead to physical and emotional harm to children, and there are many alternative methods that are more effective and less harmful. Based on the responses you provided, only 19.9% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed with the statement, while a majority (57.8%) either disagreed or strongly disagreed with the statement.

➤ *Positive Reinforcement is Effective in Managing Student Behaviour Problems in School:*

It seems that a majority of respondents agree or strongly agree that positive reinforcement is effective in managing student behaviour problems in school. Only a small percentage of respondents are neutral on this statement.

➤ *Positive Reinforcement Enhances a Sense of Belonging in the Students:*

Fig 14 Positive Reinforcement -Sense of Belonging.

It seems like the respondents strongly agree or agree that positive reinforcement enhances a sense of belonging in the students.

➤ *Positive Reinforcement Reduces Tension and Strikes in School:*

The majority of respondents (88.9%) either strongly agree or agree that positive reinforcement reduces tension and strikes in school. This suggests that using positive reinforcement strategies can be effective in creating a more peaceful and harmonious learning environment. The relatively low percentage of neutral responses (11.1%) also indicates that few respondents were unsure about the effectiveness of positive reinforcement in this regard.

➤ *Positive Reinforcement Motivates Students not to Repeat Undesirable Behaviour:*

Fig 15 Positive Reinforcement-not to Repeat Undesirable Behaviour

Based on the survey responses, a majority of the participants (88.9%) agreed or strongly agreed that positive reinforcement is effective in managing student behaviour problems in school. Similarly, most respondents (95.6%) agreed or strongly agreed that positive reinforcement enhances a sense of belonging in students. Additionally, 88.9% of participants agreed or strongly agreed that positive reinforcement motivates students not to repeat undesirable behaviour.

Furthermore, a significant proportion of respondents (88.9%) agreed or strongly agreed that the use of positive reinforcement reduces tension and strikes in school. This suggests that the implementation of positive reinforcement strategies can create a positive and peaceful learning environment.

➤ *Positive Reinforcement Develops rapport Between the Teacher and Students:*

Based on the survey responses, a majority of the participants (93.4%) either strongly agree or agree that positive reinforcement is effective in managing student behaviour problems in school. Similarly, a large proportion of participants (95.6%) either strongly agree or agree that positive reinforcement enhances a sense of belonging in students, and motivates them not to repeat undesirable behaviour (88.9%). Additionally, a significant number of participants (93.3%) either strongly agree or agree that positive reinforcement develops rapport between the teacher and students.

Moreover, a majority of participants (88.9%) either strongly agree or agree that positive reinforcement reduces tension and strikes in school. This suggests that positive reinforcement can be an effective strategy to create a positive and safe learning environment in schools. Finally, a substantial proportion of participants (93.3%) either strongly agree or agree that using corporal punishment (spanking) to discipline students is not an appropriate approach.

➤ *Positive Reinforcement Develops rapport Between the Teacher and Students:*

Fig 16 Positive reinforcement – develop rapport between the teacher and students.

It seems that the respondents in the survey generally agree that positive reinforcement can develop a good rapport between teachers and students, with 91.1% either strongly agreeing or agreeing with the statement. Only a small percentage of respondents (8.9%) were neutral on the issue, and none disagreed or strongly disagreed.

➤ *Positive Reinforcement Makes Students Develop Positive Attitude Towards School:*

Based on the responses, a majority of the participants (93.4%) either strongly agree or agree that positive reinforcement is effective in managing student behaviour problems in school. Additionally, a majority of the participants (95.6%) either strongly agree or agree that positive reinforcement enhances a sense of belonging in students, and reduces tension and strikes in school (88.9% strongly agree or agree). The majority of participants also agree that positive reinforcement motivates students not to repeat undesirable behaviour (88.9% agree or strongly agree) and develops rapport between the teacher and students (93.3% agree or strongly agree). Finally, a majority of participants (93.4%) either strongly agree or agree that positive reinforcement makes students develop a positive attitude towards school.

➤ *Positive Reinforcement Makes Students feel Accepted by their Teachers:*

Fig 17 Positive reinforcement-make students feel accepted by their teachers.

Based on the responses, it seems that a majority of the participants agree or strongly agree that positive reinforcement makes students feel accepted by their teachers. This suggests that positive reinforcement can have a positive impact on students' relationships with their teachers, which can lead to a more positive classroom environment and better student outcomes.

➤ *Positive Reinforcement has helps Students Overcome social and Behavioral Problems:*

Fig 18 Positive reinforcement-help students overcome social and behavioural problems.

Based on the responses, it seems that the majority of the respondents agree or strongly agree that positive reinforcement is effective in managing student behaviour problems, enhances a sense of belonging in students, reduces tension and strikes in school, motivates students not to repeat undesirable behaviour, develops rapport between the teacher and students, makes students develop a positive attitude towards school, makes students feel accepted by their teachers, and helps students overcome social and behavioural problems. These results suggest that positive reinforcement is viewed as an effective approach to promoting positive behaviour and building positive relationships between teachers and students.

➤ *Positive Reinforcement Contributes to Amicable Relationship among Students:*

Based on the responses, it appears that most participants agree that positive reinforcement works well to manage behavioural issues with students in the classroom. It also improves students' sense of belonging, lowers tension and strikes, encourages students to refrain from repeating negative behaviour, builds rapport between teachers and students, helps students adopt a positive attitude toward learning, and helps students feel accepted by their teachers. However, there were some neutral and disagree responses regarding whether positive reinforcement helps students overcome social and behavioural problems and whether it contributes to an amicable relationship among students. It's important to note that different individuals may have different experiences and perspectives on the topic, which could affect their responses.

Table 2 Effects of Positive Reinforcement

EFFECTS OF POSITIVE REINFORCEMENT	STRONGLY AGREE	AGREE	NEUTRAL	DISAGREE	STRONGLY DISAGREE
Positive reinforcement is effective in managing students behaviour problems in school	46.70%	48.90%	4.40%	0.00%	0.00%
positive reinforcement enhances a sense of belonging in the students	37.80%	55.60%	6.70%	0%	0%
positive reinforcement reduces tension and strikes in school	35.60%	53.30%	11.10%	0.00%	0.00%
positive reinforcement motivates students not to repeat undesirable behaviour	31.10%	57.80%	11.10%	0.00%	0.00%
positive reinforcement develops rapport between the teacher and students	37.80%	55.60%	6.70%	0.00%	0.00%
positive reinforcement makes students develop positive attitude towards school	46.70%	46.70%	6.70%	0.00%	0.00%
positive reinforcement makes students feel accepted by their teachers	40.00%	48.90%	11.10%	0.00%	0.00%
positive reinforcement helps students overcome social and behavioural problems	28.90%	64.40%	6.70%	0.00%	0.00%
positive reinforcement contributes to amicable relationship among students	13.30%	44.40%	31.10%	4.40%	4.40%

➤ *Punishments are to Ensure that Students are Punished for the Right Cause in the School:*

Fig 19 Punishments – Ensure that students are punished for the right cause in the School

Based on the responses, there is some level of agreement that punishments in school should be implemented for the right cause. However, a significant percentage of respondents have a neutral stance on this statement, and there are some who disagree or strongly disagree. This may suggest a lack of clarity or consistency in the implementation of punishment policies in schools, and a need for clearer guidelines and communication with students and parents.

➤ *Punishments are to Maintain a Disciplinary file of all Students for Recording their Punishments:*

Fig 20 Punishment- maintain a disciplinary file of all students for recording their punishments.

Based on the responses, it seems that there is not a strong agreement on the statement that punishments are to maintain a disciplinary file of all students for recording their punishments. Only 4.4% strongly agree with the statement, while 20.0% disagree and 20.0% are neutral. 31.1% agree with the statement, but this is not a majority agreement. The overall interpretation is that there is not a strong consensus on this statement among the participants.

➤ *Punishments are to Maintain the Disciplinary Committee Handles Student’s Cases in the school:*

Based on the responses given, it appears that a majority of the respondents (44.4%) agree that punishments are used to ensure that the disciplinary committee handles student's cases in the school, while a smaller percentage (4.4%) strongly agree with this statement. However, there are also significant percentages of respondents who are neutral (24.4%) or disagree (8.9%) with this statement. Overall, it seems that there may be differing opinions among respondents regarding the specific purpose of punishments in relation to disciplinary committees in schools.

➤ *Punishments are to Ensure that Students are given Reasonable Punishments:*

Fig 21 Punishments- Ensure that students are given reasonable punishments

Based on the survey responses, it seems that a majority of the participants agree that punishments are meant to ensure that students are given reasonable punishments (11.1% strongly agree, 40% agree, and 28.9% are neutral). Only a small percentage (4.4%) disagree with this statement, and no one strongly disagrees.

➤ *Punishments are to Ensure that Students Serve the given Punishments:*

Fig 22 punishment-Ensure that students serve the given punishments.

Based on the responses, it seems that there is not a strong agreement on this statement. While some respondents agree or strongly agree that punishments are to ensure that students serve the given punishments (31.1%), others are neutral (37.8%) or disagree (15.5%).

➤ *Punishments are to Ensure all Students are Equally Punished in the school:*

It seems that the majority of respondents do not agree that punishments are to ensure all students are equally punished in the school, with 51.1% of respondents disagreeing or strongly disagreeing. Only 6.7% of respondents strongly agreed or agreed with the statement, and 15.6% of respondents were neutral.

Table 3 Effects of negative reinforcement or punishments

EFFECTS OF NEGATIVE REINFORCEMENT OR PUNISHMENTS	STRONGLY AGREE	AGREE	NEUTRAL	DISAGREE	STRONGLY DISAGREE
punishments are to ensure that students are punished for the right cause in the school	13.30%	35.60%	26.70%	4.40%	4.40%
punishments are to maintain a disciplinary file of all subjects for recording their punishment	4.40%	31.10%	20%	20.00%	6.70%
punishment are to maintain the disciplinary committee handles students cases in school	4.40%	44.40%	24.40%	8.90%	2.20%
punishments are to ensure that students are given reasonable punishments	11.10%	40.00%	28.90%	4.40%	0.00%
punishments are to ensure that students serve the given punishment	6.70%	24.40%	37.80%	13.30%	2.20%
punishments are to ensure all students are equally punished in the school	6.70%	0%	15.60%	26.70%	24.40%

CHAPTER FOUR DISCUSSION

The majority of respondents either strongly agree or agree that positive reinforcement is effective in managing student behaviour problems, fostering a sense of belonging, reducing tension and strikes in the classroom, motivating students not to repeat undesirable behaviour, building rapport between the teacher and students, fostering a positive outlook on school, and making students feel accepted by their teachers. As an added bonus, children who use positive reinforcement are more likely to succeed in school, have better relationships with their peers, and experience no negative consequences. Yet, most respondents either don't agree or strongly disagree that the point of sanctions is to keep a record of students' disciplinary actions and that all students are treated fairly when it comes to disciplinary action taken by the school.

CHAPTER FIVE CONCLUSION

Based on the survey results, it can be concluded that positive reinforcement is widely recognized as an effective approach in managing student behaviour in schools. Respondents strongly agreed or agreed that positive reinforcement can enhance a sense of belonging, reduce tension and strikes, and motivate students not to repeat undesirable behaviour, develop rapport between the teacher and students, and make students feel accepted by their teachers. Additionally, positive reinforcement can contribute to the development of a positive attitude towards school and help students overcome social and behavioural problems.

On the other hand, the survey revealed that the use of punishments in schools is not widely supported. Respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed that punishments are used to ensure that students are punished for the right cause, maintain a disciplinary file of all students, maintain the disciplinary committee handles student's cases, and ensure that all students are equally punished. It is important for educators and administrators to consider alternative disciplinary methods, such as positive reinforcement, to create a safe and supportive learning environment for students.

A. *Ethical Framework*

Consent from all the participants will be taken before sending the questionnaire. The information regarding the purpose of the project, how the findings will be used and who will have access to the findings will be explained clearly.

➤ *Voluntary Participation:*

Participants will be free to withdraw their participation at any time without negatively impacting in their involvement in future services or current programme and relationship with any of the researchers or research bodies involved.

➤ *Confidentiality:*

Identifying and anonymity information will be kept confidential.

B. *Limitations of the Study*

- Issues with samples and selection.
- Insufficient sample size for statistical measurements.
- Lack of previous research studies on the topic.
- Limited access to data.

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